

Report of the 1st joint workshop LIFE MICA - RIPARIAS

Participants¹

Ben van der Wijden, Jasmijn Hillaert, Damiano Oldoni, Emma Cartuyvels, Stijn Van Onsem, Nick De Meersman, Dan Sloomakers, Mirjam Boonstra, Lilja Fromme, Claudia Maistrelli, Friederike Gethöffer, Heiko Fritz, Dolf Moerkens, Kevin Smith, Ana Nunes, Ricardo Scalera, Valentina La Morgia, Piero Genovesi, Lucilla Carnevali, Joaquin Vicente, Rachele Vada, Bernd Reichelt, Egbert Strauß, Linus Günther, Christian Boestfleisch, Quentin Groom, Reinhardt Strubbe, Olivier Beck, Xavier Vermeersch, Nicolas Pardon, Julie Goffette, Jérémie Guyon, Dido Gosse, Caroline De Jonghe, Etienne Branquart, Eric Joiris, Pierre Joye, Augustin Smoos, Tim Adriaens, Bram D'hondt, Ingrid Marchand, Christine Fournier, Pascal Fournier, Maylis Fayet, Christelle Bellanger, Cynthia Llas, Myriam Labadesse, Delphine Morin, Steeve Mathieu, Ana Klenovsek, Guillaume Body, Albert Arnaud, Anke Stefens, Arnaud Alber, Lukas Ittner, Benjamin Waldmann, Annette Scharmann, Frank Huysentruyt, Jim Casaer, Per-Arne Ahlen, Tiago de Sousa, Wojciech Solarz, Walter Oudshoorn, Karel van Moer, Benoît Pisanu, Wolf van Lier, Daniel Nuijten, Sonia Illanas, Sander Devisscher, Agnès Merlet, Elena Tricarico, Frédérique Steen, Peter Desmet, Lien Reyserhove, Andrea Monaco, José Antonio Blanco

Presentations

- [The need for a data exchange format on IAS / wildlife management](#) (Damiano Oldoni, Jasmijn Hillaert & Tim Adriaens, LIFE RIPARIAS)
- Management activities, reporting and data flows in LIFE MICA (Emma Cartuyvels, LIFE MICA)
- The Enetwild standard for reporting on wildlife management and data exchange between Member States (Joaquin Vicente & Guillaume Body, Enetwild)
- Management activities, reporting and data flows in American mink control in Charente and Charente-Maritime (Ingrid Marchand, Life VISON)

¹ The participant list could be not exhaustive or include people who subscribed but didn't attend.

- Management activities, reporting and data flows in rat control in French Overseas Territories (Delphine Morin, Life BIODIV'OM)
- A provisional template for reporting IAS management in Life projects (Riccardo Scalera, IUCN, ISSG)

Break-outs

Four break-out rooms have been organized. Acronyms added for referencing:

- [IAS Plant management - terrestrial and aquatic](#) (Plants)
- [Trapping - terrestrial and semi-aquatic](#) (Trap-tsa)
- [Trapping - aquatic](#) (Trap-a)
- [Shooting and hunting \(mammals, birds\)](#) (Shoot)

The summarized results follow here below.

What should be reported when performing an IAS management action?

What is **essential** when **reporting** on Invasive Alien Species (IAS) management interventions? And what is **optional**? Think of the *who*, the *where*, the *when*, the *what*, any reporting requirements your organization or your project might be subjected to, or any aspects you consider useful to capture when managing a species.

What should be reported	Essential/ Optional	Comments
Project level information (metadata)		
Management objective - Prevention of introduction, - Prevention of entry, - Prevention of spread, - Early detection and rapid eradication, - Eradication of established populations, - Control of established populations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suppression, complete reproductive removal - Zero management 	essential	There is a framework for the management of IAS available which could provide a vocabulary and definitions (Robertson et al. 2020 biol inv)
Procedures & Outcomes	essential	
Management time frame	essential	
Management organization(s)	essential	
Management coordinator	essential	
Management area	essential	
Temporal information		
Date	essential	
Time	essential	
Management period / Hunting season	optional	

Personal information		
Management organization	essential	
Manager profile (e.g. field worker, contractor, volunteer)	optional	
Contact/personal information	optional	
Geographical information		
Location (point coordinates, lines or polygons)	essential	River basin management often uses line transects
Spatial vectors of areas (e.g. hunting grounds, municipalities)	essential	When not precise coordinates available
Land cover (e.g. natural, seminatural, built up environment)	optional	
Land ownership status (public/private)	optional	
Management information		
Technique (e.g. killing or eradication method)	essential	Potentially important to separate management method from techniques for killing and dispatch (e.g. live trapping but with euthanasia)
Material deployed (e.g. type & number of traps, number of days, type of firearm or munition)	essential	Type of ammunition: optional
Baiting information	essential/optional	Type of bait used, but also whether prebaiting was applied, this could also be part of method/technique
Effort (man hours)	essential	
Other effort measures	essential	If any
Media as proof of management	optional/essential	Essential for proving the death of some target

		species, e.g. American mink vs European mink (Shoot)
Specimen information		
Target species (one or more)	essential	
Quantity of specimens	essential	
Age class of the specimen	optional	
Sex of the specimen	optional	
Size of the specimen	optional	
Weight of the specimen	optional	
Reproductive status of the specimen	optional	
Diseases encountered in specimen	optional	
Non-target effects of management		
Environmental, biodiversity	essential	
Socio-economic, human health	essential	
bycatch	essential	Shoot: optional and expressed as “Non-target species affected”
Management of the residuals (green waste, contaminated lands)		
Ethics: animal welfare impacts (e.g. wounded animals)		
Public perception	optional	
Possible threats	optional	
Additional restoration measures	optional	
Safety measures for personnel	optional	

How is/should it be reported?

For any of the topics you identified useful for reporting on IAS management, provide **information on *how* these are currently or should best be reported**. We are looking especially at the units used, standard vocabularies of values that you know of or that you use. Start with the essential ones, but you can of course also add elements for the optional things to report.

Reporting (e.g. method, result, non-target effect...)	Unit (e.g. density, surface area, number)	Vocabulary/values/reference used	Issues encountered
Management objective		EU IAS Reg objectives: Prevention Surveillance Rapid eradication Eradication (*eradication of entire population within a MS) Control Containment	Objective might change over time or per area if reporting at project level
Effectiveness	Categories of effectiveness Yes/no	Refer back to management objective	
Spatial information	Coordinates; Polygons	WKT or Shapefiles	Difficulties comparing coordinates with polygons
Method/technique		Highest level of detail possible	
Effort taken	Man hours spent	Man hours spent are the best measure to quantify costs	avoid using monetary terms (xx €), as this is confounded by many aspects CPUE for aquatic animals

Target species		Scientific name Common name (synonyms)	Allow more than one species
Age class of specimen		Neonate, juvenile, adult	
Quantity of specimens	Number of individuals	Integer	
Bycatch	Number of individuals per species	Integer	Important for communication in relation to target species

Any issues with respect to management reporting?

If from your experience, there are **issues with reporting (a particular aspect of) IAS management**, please add them to the table. Think of obstacles to management reporting (these can be general to all aspects of course), specific aspects that are not reported but should be, hindrances to capturing data, lack of knowledge on how to report, dataflows, exchange of data or other.

Description of issue
Links between databases (e.g. the same animal reported in an observation database, management database, EU's NOTSYS database, a genetic sample database...).
When collected by hunters not shared (variation by countries) in a good spatial temporal/resolution as often there are only reporting obligations per game management unit. Privacy issue?
It's very difficult to collect good quality data on shooting when voluntary operators (hunters) are involved. Reporting is not always mandatory (es. coypu). Moreover mean age of hunters (in Italy at least) is very high so is not so easy to ask them to use a smartphone app or other technologies
Mandatory vs. non-mandatory reporting. (E.g. Flanders: roe is mandatory, muntjac is not...)
The legal status of a species may confuse people reporting (E.g. Flanders: all game species go in one form, but alien species go in another.)(Don't get me wrong: there are good reasons to do that, hunting is sustainable harvest vs eradication for IAS!)
Lack of communication and marketing on the management reporting tool
Integration of information about the involvement of volunteers: what is their profile? Range of experience is pronounced
Non-target effects: not always recorded in specific projects
Lack of a reporting tool for e.g. national agencies to know what is happening in the field!
Strive for one single standard, valid for all different taxonomic groups. Not an easy task.
Main issues with effort reporting
Volunteers could be not as exact in reporting as professional IAS field managers and data could be missing or less detailed. A management reporting tool should be flexible enough to

cope with these differences.
Lack of a standard

Use cases

At LIFE RIPARIAS, we created an open GitHub repository, [manIAS](#), to better structure the development of a **community driven** data model and data exchange format for the management of IAS. So, implicitly we are using manIAS to name this data model and data exchange format. Can you find a better name? Contribute to this [first issue](#). You are welcome!

Collecting **use cases** from different taxonomic groups and IAS management techniques is very important to develop and continuously improve manIAS. How to contribute? Send an export with an example of your IAS management data. It doesn't need to be huge, but representative and as complete as possible. Please contact Damiano Oldoni (damiano.oldoni@inbo.be), Tim Adriaens (tim.adriaens@inbo.be) or place an [issue](#).

TDWG2022

LIFE RIPARIAS will be present at **TDWG 2022**, the annual conference of the [Biodiversity Information Standards](#) (TDWG). To make the best out of it, we would like to submit a proposal for an **organized session** about the need of a data exchange format for IAS and wildlife management. Are you interested to participate and to be involved in drafting the session? Let us know by contacting Lien Reyserhove (lien.reyserhove@inbo.be), Quentin Groom (quentin.groom@plantentuinmeise.be), Damiano Oldoni (damiano.oldoni@inbo.be) or Tim Adriaens (tim.adriaens@inbo.be). Deadline: **15 April 2022**.